

*Emotional intelligence and balance between work and life in employees'*_____

_____ **Dr. Elsida SINAJ** _____

DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, PSYCHOLOGY AND SPORTS
EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY OF TIRANA
elsida.sinaj@uet.edu.al

_____ **Msc. Elisa GJONAJ** ² _____

PSYCHOLOGIST
e.gjonaj23@gmail.com

Abstract

This study sets to explore the impact of Emotional Intelligence and work-life balance on the quality of life at work. The study champion consists of the workers of various public and private enterprises in the city of Tirana. Participants in this study were a young group, newly acquainted with work and as such may still be in an effort to balance not only work-family conflicts but also to manage emotional intelligence in the workplace. The results showed that there is no correlation between EI and Work-Family Conflict (WFC). However, it turns out that there is a statistically significant correlation in the negative value between emotional intelligence conflicts and work-

¹ **Dr. Elsida Sinaj** has been actively engaged in the Student Care Office, where she also holds the position of Dean of Students. Elsida has an experience in scientific research work mainly in the field of Health Psychology and Counseling in issues related to quality and lifestyle, chronic diseases and psychological disorders in the third age, health behaviors in students and teachers, personality traits, career counseling etc. Elsida also worked as a Mental Health Specialist at the Shkoder Regional Health Directorate in the Office of Psychosocial Services, she has experience in the field of teaching, where she worked as a teacher in 9-year and secondary schools. She has published various articles in scientific journals at home and abroad, as well as participated in several national and international scientific conferences.

² **Msc. Elisa Gjonaj** has finished her master studies on organizational psychology and she actually is working as a human resources specialist in a business company.

family (WFC) conflicts. The study also found a statistically significant correlation in workers participating in this study, related to Emotional Intelligence of Workers and Quality of Life. Emotional intelligence, work-family conflicts, and quality of life in workers in this study presented a statistically important correlation with variables such as gender, education, duration in current work, and work experience as a whole, thus proving all three hypotheses. Referring to the results of this study, it would be appropriate to develop studies addressing a large number of champions, as well as differentiated into one or two separate sectors. This can provide more knowledge about the variables taken in the study. This may provide more insight into the results obtained in the study.

Keywords: *Emotional intelligence, conflict, WFC, FWC, balance, life, work, quality of life, work, Tirana.*

1. Introduction

Globalization, new technologies, and business restructuring in the century we are living in are challenging the long-established patterns of work and workplace, which impose new burdens on individuals and their families. Jobs are becoming more and more dynamic, with frequent changes which have an impact on the mental and emotional health of employees who work to have jobs. As such, they require some kind of flexibility or some kind of intelligence in addition to the technical and intellectual one like IQ, but better adaptability and management of human emotions. This type of intelligence is called Emotional Intelligence (EI). (EI) is seen as closely linked to mental health and happiness, as analogies to each other. The definition according to (Mayer & Salovey, 1997: 10) is considered: “*The ability to evaluate and express emotions; the ability to manage feelings and have a simpler mind; the ability to understand personal and others’ emotions, as well as to adjust emotions*.” This term is now increasingly being widely used in various public and non-public organizations and businesses. According to (Nanda & Randhawa, 2020) EI is considered one of the best and most effective skills an employee can have, helping him to be more productive and emotionally healthy. On the other hand, EI is considered a very important predictor in the manifestation of performance in the workplace. According to (Talentsmart, n.d.) about 90% of employees who have high performance at work have high emotional intelligence. Companies today demand that the worker be psychologically calm in order for the company’s objectives to be achieved as clearly as possible. In recent years, competition in the labor market has increased significantly

and they are constantly working under stress. Achieving the highest possible productivity is one of the biggest challenges for organizations and companies today. Based on this, the main objective of companies is oriented towards the concepts of employee well-being, work-life balance, and family, which are thought to lead to increased efficiency and productivity of employees at work. “*Employee well-being is defined as “the overall quality of an employee’s experience and functioning at work”*” (Grant et al., 2007: 52) and has three essential dimensions, psychological, physical, and social well-being.

An individual’s EI is considered to reduce this type of balance or this type of conflict, by improving it. Individual’s EI is thought to reduce this type of balance or this type of conflict, improving it. In a study conducted by (Basu, 2019), where the main focus was to occur a balance between working life, was in the study participated 2000 in Indian, it turned out that 67% of them think about work and when they are not at work. It is also a well-known fact that WLB contributes to the health and well-being of employees and helps reduce stress and prevent burnout in the workplace. Therefore, this balance sheet is an extremely important aspect of a healthy work environment that should not be ignored by companies. Therefore, for the above, this chapter will be discussed in more detail some key aspects of this study, such as emotional intelligence, work-family balance, and quality of life, and, above all, will be presented, the main findings of how these three variables stand between them in the context of literature review in this regard, and various studies conducted by foreign authors.

Emotional Intelligence (EI)

Plato was the first to trace EI as “*all learning has an emotional basis*” (Wharam, 2009: 7), or further, the psychologist Thorndike (1920) gave this concept a clearer and more consistent meaning. He was the first to invent the term social intelligence, defining it as the ability to understand and act appropriately in human relations” (p. 228), the other in all kinds of relations, considering social intelligence a very important process in the lives of each. Essentially, this intelligence (SI) is the ability to perceive internal situations, motivations, and behaviors of yourself and others. In the late 20th century, the term social intelligence began to take on new and deeper meanings not only socially but also educationally, as more influential than general social intelligence. This theory was further developed by other psychologists where si suggested that multiple intelligence included personal intelligence that relies on interpersonal intelligence (an ability to connect with others) and intrapersonal intelligence (an ability to understand, motivate and manage oneself). The term further enriched Salovey and Mayer (1990) who called it ‘Emotional Intelligence’ as a

derivative of Social Intelligence, which means the individual's ability to control personal emotions and those of others, adjusting the way of thinking and acting (p. 189). Mayer and Salovey further continued to determine emotional intelligence (EI) by taking elements into consideration by compiling a model that the main focus had individual abilities. It was Goleman that in 1995 brought about a false change over EI. Goleman suggests that EI should be viewed as the perspectives of mixed traits or patterns as one's ability to motivate oneself and move forward in the face of disappointment; to control impulses and delay pleasure; to regulate one's mood and to keep anxiety from the kidnapping of the ability to think; sensitive and hopeful. In 1997 Goleman redefined EI as the capacity to understand our feelings and other persons, influencing increased motivation and increased capacity to manage feelings, and our emotions in relation to others. The widely accepted scientific definition of EI is the ability to monitor our own and others' emotions and to use the information to have effective social relationships. In institutions where constant changes occur, workers need to have a highly accompanied and productive IE. The authors suggest that to be a good worker in (the family, thirst work) we need to have a combination between IQ and EI.

The key qualities that distinguish successful from unsuccessful executives are the core competencies (or apparently embedded) EI. Failed executives seem to have weaker emotional control, despite strengths in cognitive skills and technical expertise. Therefore, emotional intelligence leads to effective performance. IE has been studied using different conceptualizations, the most popular ones being the skill-based model (Mayer et al., 2016), the feature-based model and the mixed model. Although these models conceive of EI very differently, everyone agrees when it comes to explaining EI relationships with different psychological and psychosocial factors as well as influencing work environments to manage and enhance emotions, work attitudes, and outcomes between employees in the workplace. Emotionally intelligent people are often better able to cope with life activities and they have a positive as well as productive mindset which often involves affective awareness. In the context of the affective revolution in organizational psychology, IE is defended as a key predictor of organizational outcomes including job satisfaction, job engagement, job stress, workplace outburst, and ill health (Alvi, 2018).

Emotional intelligence in the workplace

Being productive in the workplace and with a high EI means having functional emotional intelligence. EI has an important role in human health, including happiness elements, psychological well-being in the workplace, home, society, and family. In the meta-analytical study of Schutte (2002) in which 7898

participants participated, the results showed that EI was positively related to good psychological and physical health (Schutte et al, 2002). While in a 2010 study conducted by Faguy, low EI was associated with the emergence of violent behaviors and dangerous health behaviors such as drug use, alcohol, and involvement in criminal behavior (Faguy, 2012). Researchers Adeoye and Torubelli (2011) in their study found that EI affects the psychological connection that the employee creates with the institution where he works, even EI could be predictive in the impact it has on the regulation of human relations and commitment to achieving goals. of the institution. Cherniss (2000) explained that emotionally intelligent people are more cooperative and more committed, elements that are important for productivity in an organization. Salami (2008) suggests that understanding and managing our emotions, in line with understanding the emotions of others, are elements that can influence the attitudes of colleagues towards each other towards bosses, and so on. According to Adeoye and Torubelli (2011) relationship management is a personal capacity to understand others and relationships, which includes the ability to resolve conflicts effectively, be negotiable, be social, friendly, etc. Emotional intelligence increases the potential to have a clearer understanding of oneself and others by including social situations with different dynamics.

Work-Life Balance

The concept of a work-life or work-family balance was used in the late 1970s to describe the balance between an individual's work and his or her social family life. Nowadays working hours have changed, and this change has occurred in both genders. WLB (Work and Life Balance) soon became known for dynamic changes in the workplace and this is already a worldwide phenomenon (Ashwini, 2017). Vajiravel (2015) in his holist study on WLB made a division of the results into 3 parts: Good job-related results (e.g. high job performance, high job satisfaction, low work frustration, missing long-term days off), Results not related to work (i.e.: High satisfaction from life, high satisfaction from family time, low rates of conflicts with family members, etc.), and results related with stress (i.e.: low emotional tiredness, low depression, low anxiety, etc.) Also, another study (Vajiravel, 2015) suggests that the effects of WLB include high-quality work, work motivation, job satisfaction, quality of health and free time with family, society, conflicts regarding work, burnout, and health condition are some of the negative effects of a misbalance in the working life. The question arises: Can EI be predictive in relation to the work-life balance of workers? How does EI relate to employee productivity in the workplace? (Faguy, 2012) discovered that the evaluation and the expression of emotions, needs a good interpretation of verbal and nonverbal information.

The notion showed that the interpretation of unspoken messages of the face mimic, body language, tone of the voice and the words chosen are the key to understand the emotions of the others. Faguy (2012) again discovered that the regulation and management of emotions it is something that everyone does, but an emotionally intelligent person does it better and it uses a certain method to achieve a specific purpose. Ravichandran et al., (2011) showed that the workers should increase their emotional ability together with their technical abilities that these ones on the other side increase the emotional intelligence, work productivity and push energetic employees to be more connected to their work. Does EI reflected in the personal life of an employee and is there any connection between intelligence and WLB? The motivation of people to be engaged in work is a well-known problem, this is related to the workload of workers, who are forced to do a lot of work often and beyond their capacity, behaviors, attitudes, and emotions related to a role, may spread to another person and they may not control the emotions when they go to their families home. (Ravichandran et al., 2011).The constructs itself makes it difficult to describe what is WLB. Every definition depends on personal choices which are individual. While moving through different life milestones, from childhood until you are old, roles that play can change, increase, decrease or disappear. Moreover, the focus put on every played role will change too with the change of life circumstances. On the other hand, WLB term was created in 1986 in response to increasing disturbance from individuals and organizations so that the work cannot influence in the quality of family life and vice versa, creating the concepts of conflicts of family-work (FWC) and conflicts of work-family (WFC).

The first one is referred in the sense that work can influence in the family life (WIF), while the second is the influence of family into work (FIW). With other words, from the perspective of absence, the time dedicated to work can be interpreted as time taken from family life. Competition, high demands on work, and responsibilities at home have become very important for employees due to major changes in demographics and the workplace such as: big number of female workforce (couples with double careers), transformation in family structures (increase in single parenting), disagreement of long hours jobs, increase of 24/7 job methods and technological advances. Referring to these many changes and conflicts that they create between roles that individuals have, organizations get under pressure to create different policies that aim to ease the effort of employees to fulfill their work and personal commitments. The method to achieve and increase WLB it's an important topic in Human Resource Management field and has been important for employers, employees, government, academics and mass media (Saraswat & Choudhary, 2017).

2. Methodology

Study purpose and objectives

The aim of the study is to investigate the impact of Emotional intelligence and WLB on the quality of life of employees. The objectives are:

Hypothesis of the study:

H1: Exists an important statistical correlation between Emotional Intelligence and Work-Family conflicts and vice versa for employees.

H2: Exists an important statistical correlation between emotional intelligence and life quality for employees.

H3: Exists an important statistical correlation between demographics, emotional intelligence, WFC and life quality for employees.

Research instruments

Emotional Intelligence scale, developed by Schutte et al., 1997; FWC scale developed by Netemeyer et al., 1996; Quality of life scale (QOLS) developed by Flanagan. 1978 and renewed again by Flanagan in 1982.

3. Results analysis

In this study the above hypothesis will be tested and will be analyzed with different variables taken in analysis to better understand their relation.

TABLE NO.1 Correlation between IE, FWC and WFC, Hypothesis no.1

Emotional Intelligence (IE)	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	102		
Family-Work Conflict (FWC)	Pearson Correlation	-.424**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	102	102	
Work-Family Conflict (WFC)	Pearson Correlation	.024	.609**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.810	.000	
	N	102	102	102

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table shows that exists an important statistical correlation between FWC and EI of the interviewees of the study. The correlation is $r = -.424$, negative value. This means that these 2 variables are negatively connected with one another. The greater the Emotional Intelligence, the lower the Family-Work Conflict and vice versa. From the analysis table can be seen that there is a positive correlation of FWC and WFC. This correlation is with a value of $r = .609$, which means that the interviewees that expressed one high variable, had the tendency to do the same for the other variable and vice versa.

The results show that there is no correlation of emotional intelligence and the Work-Family Conflict. ***We can say that the first hypothesis of this study is fully proven true.***

TABLE NO.2 Correlation between IE and Life Quality, Hypothesis no.2

		Emotional Intelligence	Quality of Life
Emotional Intelligence (IE)	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	102	
Quality of Life	Pearson Correlation	.500**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	102	102

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table shows that exists an important statistical correlation between Emotional Intelligence among the sample of this study with the Quality of Life that they stated. The correlation has a value of $r = .500$, a positive value which means that the higher the EI, the higher also the Quality of Life. ***Can be said that the second hypothesis of this study is fully proven true.***

TABLE NO.3 Correlation between IE, WFC, FWC, Quality of Life and demographic variables of the sample.

		IE	Quality of Life	Gender	FWC	WFC	Age	Education	Duration in current work	Work Experience
IE	Pearson Correlation	1								
	Sig. (2-tailed)									
	N	102								

Quality of Life	Pearson Correlation	.500**	1							
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000								
	N	102	102							
Gender	Pearson Correlation	-.028	.102	1						
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.779	.310							
	N	102	102	102						
FWC	Pearson Correlation	-.424**	-.251*	-.153	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.011	.125						
	N	102	102	102	102					
WFC	Pearson Correlation	.024	.030	.391**	.609**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.810	.767	.000	.000					
	N	102	102	102	102	102				
Age	Pearson Correlation	-.125	-.563**	-.116	-.079	-.131	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.212	.000	.244	.429	.188				
	N	102	102	102	102	102	102			
Education	Pearson Correlation	-.209*	-.097	.557**	-.100	-.378**	.179	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.035	.335	.000	.315	.000	.071			
	N	102	102	102	102	102	102	102		
Duration in current work	Pearson Correlation	.213	-.171	-.162	-.439**	-.001	.643**	.004	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.032	.087	.105	.000	.995	.000	.966		
	N	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	
Work Experience	Pearson Correlation	-.101	-.286**	.000	-.378**	-.141	.767**	.321**	.759**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.313	.004	1.000	.000	.157	.000	.001	.000	
	N	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table shows the results of the variables of this study and their correlation with one another. In the 3rd hypothesis, the study wants to understand better the relationship between EI, WFC and Quality of Life with their demographics. Gender seems to have an important statistical correlation with FWC. This correlation is high with a value of $r=.391$ which tells that female have a higher tendency to bring their family problems at work. Because of female are the ones that take care of the house, children etc., it is understandable that they tend to have difficulty in balancing this emotional conflict in their workplace. Also, this sample had a higher number of females.

4. Conclusions

Nowadays, employees have a lot of challenges in their workplace. Globalization, new technologies and business reconstruction in this century, challenge the models that exist in the workplace, which impose new challenges in individuals and their families. The workplaces are getting more dynamic, with frequent changes that have an impact on the mental and emotional health of employees that work in these workplaces. As such, they seek for a flexibility or some kind of intelligence together with the technical and intellectual like IQ, but also a better management of emotions. This kind of intelligence is called the Emotional Intelligence. The definition of Emotional Intelligence has changed and is still changing, causing insecurity in its first definition. The identified theory to prove this research was the theory of multiple intelligence and the growing theory. Both these theories offer a base to explore the role of emotional intelligence in the work of employees. Emotional intelligence and its connection with the quality of life and more, it's a growing topic in organizations for making scientific and empiric researches. Practices of the balance between life and work are organizational intentional changes in programs or organizational culture that are created to lower the conflict from working life and to give employees the opportunity to be more effective at work and other roles. The change from the WLB practices like a tool to accommodate individual employees responsible to know their contribution in organizational performance and employee engagement it's an important change that is still "on process". Competition and high requests between work and responsibilities at home have taken a lot of importance for employees lately because of a big change in demographics and workplace like: big number of female workforce (couples with double careers), transformation in family structures (increase in single parenting), disagreement of long hours jobs, increase of 24/7 job methods and technological advancements.

Emotional intelligence, a conflict of two dimensions (WFC and FWC) that aids WLB and quality of life, is a philosophy that shows that people are an important link for institutions, given that all the productivity and performance of an institution are related to staff performance, based on this they should be treated with respect and dignity and in the best possible way. According to this principle, this scientific research is treated in the above title to understand better which are the implications regarding the emotional intelligence and the work-life balance on employees. This study is done in the city of Tirana, with a questionnaire conducted by Google Forms. Overall, the whole study is compiled in 5 main chapters, including Introduction, Literature Review, Methodology, Result Analysis and the chapter of Conclusions and Recommendations. The main objective of this

study was to research the methods of the main variables of this study. The chapter of Introduction includes the background of Emotional Intelligence, WLB and its combination to identify the actual problems. Literature review included different sources of literature that will be included in the study which were very important for the methodology and the result analysis. Different literatures were reviewed, which made it easier in finding the existence of limitation between the literature and this study. Further, the descriptive and statistical analysis was done for proving the hypothesis of the study. The questionnaire was the method of collecting the data for the study. WLB is a topic that has got a lot of attention of researchers, academics and CEOs of different organizations. Managing it in a professional way is a challenge for employees. Different organizations must try to make effective policies on WLB by increasing the quality of life, job satisfaction and encourage their employees to use their policies. This helps in increasing organizational engagement for having a better productivity, to keep the best talent and to motivate employees to make their best. This study confirms that emotional intelligence and WLB, together with quality of life are 3 variables connected very well with one another, that even create an organizational success and create a competitive advantage for organizations/companies/businesses. Human resource teams and board of directors of these organizations/companies/businesses of service must take the initiative to grow and improve the emotional intelligence skills of their employees.

Improved emotional intelligence skills will help an individual to better understand and manage his emotions and the other's, which will make the delivery of the products/services with a higher quality. So, that is why it's necessary for the managers to create a connecting bridge between the emotional intelligence and WLB in order to increase the quality of life of their employees. Good policies of WLB have a great potential in improving the employees' morale, job satisfaction, life satisfaction, performance levels and decreasing the work absence. Emotional intelligence it's an effective method for integrating, improving and securing a better life at work and at family. The understanding of the potential and talent that their employees bring, the security of changes that the employees bring in their workplace and their evaluation to make it part of organizational success. Managers and owners must concentrate in development and implementation of better policies of WLB in order to build a stable and profitable organization. Education of emotional intelligence and to make the employees to feel values should be approved by all organizations/companies/businesses.

References

Alvi, A. A. U. (2018). How does balanced work life influence the job stress, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction of employees? *WALIA Journal*, 34(1), 145– 150.

- Adeoye, H., & Torubelli, V. (2011). Emotional intelligence and human relationship management as predictors of organisational commitment. *IFE Psychologist*, 19 (2)212-226. Doi.org/10.4314/lifep.v19i2.69532.
- Ashwini, S. (2017). A comparative study on worklife balance of women employees in public and private sector banks [Doctoral dissertation, University of Mysore]. Shodhganga. <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/223299>.
- Cherniss, C., Extejn, M., Goleman D. & Weissburg, R.P. (2006). Emotional intelligence: What does the research really indicate? *Educational Psychologist*, 41(4), 239-245 marrë online në: [http://alliance.la.asu.edu/temporary/students/katie/Multiple IntelligenceEmotional.pdf](http://alliance.la.asu.edu/temporary/students/katie/Multiple%20IntelligenceEmotional.pdf).
- Faguy, K. (2012) Emotional intelligence in healthcare. *Radiologic Technology*, 83(3), 237-253.
- Grant, A. M., Christianson, M. K., & Price, R. H. (2007). Happiness, health, or relationships? Managerial practices and employee well-being tradeoffs. *The Academy of Management Perspectives*, 21(3), 51–63. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2007.26421238>.
- Grant-Vallone, E.J., & Donaldson, S.I.(2002). Understanding self-report bias in organizational behavior research, *Journal of Business and Psychology*,17:2,245- 260.
- Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ*. Bloomsbury.
- Goleman, D. (1998b, November-December). What makes a leader? *Harvard Business Review*, 93-102.
- Mayer, J. D., & Salovey, P. (1997). What is emotional intelligence? In P. Salovey & D. J. Sluyter (Eds.), *Emotional development and emotional intelligence: Educational implications* (pp. 3–31). Basic Books.
- Nanda, M. & Randhawa, G., (2020). Emotional Intelligence, Work-Life Balance, and Work-Related Well-Being: A Proposed Mediation Model. *Colombo Business Journal International Journal of Theory and Practice*. 11. 1-23. 10.4038/cbj.v11i2.62.
- Salami, S. (2008). Psychosocial factors as predictors of mentoring among nurses in Southwestern Nigeria. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 20(5), 348-363.
- Salovey, P., & Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional intelligence. *Imagination, Cognition and Personality*, 9(3), 185–211. <https://doi.org/10.2190/DUGG-P24E-52WK6CDG>.
- Saraswat Y. & Choudhary Sh., (2017). Emotional Intelligence & Work Life Balance – Study of Academicians. *Periyar Journal of Research in Business and Development Studies*, 2(1), ISSN fq. 2456-0987(O).
- Schutte N. S., Malouff J. M., Hall L. E., Haggerty D. J., Cooper J. T., Golden C. J., Dornheim L., (1998). Development and validation of a measure of emotional intelligence, *Personality and Individual Differences*, Volume 25, Issue 2, fq. 167-177, ISSN 0191-8869. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869\(98\)00001-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869(98)00001-4).
- Schutte, N.S. Malouff, J.M, Simunek, M., Hollander, S. & McKenley (2002). Characteristics of emotional well-being. *Cognition and Emotion*, 16, fq. 769-786.
- Vajiravel, R. (2015). Work life balance of women teaching staff and its impact on their job performance [Doctoral dissertation, University of Madras]. Shodhganga. <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/200130>.
- Wharam, J. (2009). *Emotional intelligence: Journey to the centre of yourself*. John Hunt Publishing.